

D6.6 Report on the results of dissemination activities

**WP6 Enabling environment and
awareness raising**

Dolores Ubide (AgriSat), Anna Osann (AgriSat),

Gregory Mygdakos (AgroApps)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730109.

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Document Information

Grant Agreement No	730109	Acronym	DIANA	
Full Title	Detection and Integrated Assessment of Non-authorized water Abstractions using EO			
Horizon 2020 Call	EO-1-2016: Downstream applications			
Type of Action	Innovation Action			
Start Date	1 st January 2017	Duration	36 Months	
Project URL	www.diana-h2020.eu			
Document URL	-			
EU Project Officer	Iulia SIMION			
Project Coordinator	Polimachi Simeonidou, Anna Osann			
Deliverable	D6.6 Report on the results of dissemination activities			
Work Package	WP6 Enabling environment and awareness raising			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M6	Actual	M6
Nature	R – Report	Dissemination Level	PU	
Lead Beneficiary	AgriSat			
Lead Author	Dolores Ubide	Email	Mariadolores.ubide@agrisat.es	
	AgriSat	Phone	+34 967 033401	
Other authors	Gregory Mygdakos (AgroApps), Anna Osann (AgriSat)			
Reviewer(s)	AgroApps			
Keywords	Dissemination, Communication			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.0	29/11/2018	[Draft]	First draft	AgriSat
V01	20/12/2018	For review		AgriSat

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Executive summary

The key for a successful dissemination and communication strategy has been the application of a common framework, providing the consortium with a common process and a set of common criteria, with the purpose to identify, monitor and select the suited dissemination channels.

Another important parameter for the success of the dissemination plan has been the direct involvement of all partners of the consortium in the process, especially those responsible for pilot implementation. All project partners have developed a sense of co-ownership of the project as they have been involved at all stages of the strategy's development. Each consortium member has responsibility for a particular aspect of the strategy's implementation, but also a shared vision and common understanding of what has to be disseminated together with a way of describing this to the audiences outside of the project that may benefit from the project work.

All dissemination activities have been in line with the protection of IPR as well as the confidentiality obligations, which were established in the Consortium Agreement (CA). All partners have actively engaged in the dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities conducted so far and are committed to continue along the lifespan of the project and beyond.

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of dissemination and communication activities carried out by the DIANA consortium during the first two years of the project. It will be updated at the end of the project in D6.7 Report on the results of Dissemination activities (2). The purpose of the dissemination activities has been to apply the dissemination strategy in pilot countries in co-operation with the local partners.

The main assets disseminated are: the DIANA data products and services; the DIANA service platform and its components including the web and mobile applications; novel knowledge generated through the implementation of the project; and the data collected during the pilot implementation.

The target groups and audience for dissemination have been water managers, authorities, farmers, agricultural cooperatives and consultancies, research and academia, NGOs and civil society groups, other stakeholders, and the general public.

The dissemination and communication material and activities that have been produced or undertaken during this period include:

- the visual identity of the project, established at the beginning of the project, aiming to set the baseline for a brand identity for the commercial service;
- a public website launched in M05 and regularly updated, to serve as a single source of information concerning the project results and activities, and to disseminate news;
- the DIANA page on Facebook, the LinkedIn group and the DIANA Twitter account, which provide platforms for communicating news and material related to DIANA to specific audiences (e.g. younger, technologically-aware farmers on Facebook), and for sharing the latest information on the DIANA services;

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- the first pilot area videos on DIANA YouTube channel;
- the first of the project's newsletters, providing information, results and events related to the project;
- specific dissemination materials used and distributed at external conferences (i.e. audience-focused presentations);
- representation in conferences and media as well as the publication of scientific papers, enhancing DIANA's visibility and enabling the development of a solid network amongst agricultural and Earth Observation (EO) academic and industrial stakeholders at both European and regional level.

All planned actions for the first and second year of the project have been carried out successfully and according to the plan. All consortium partners took part in the respective dissemination activities and contributed to achieving maximum attention and awareness beyond the project consortium.

All dissemination and communication activities are planned to be enhanced and amplified in the last project year. With convincing outcomes of pilot deployment and co-evaluation in hand, the intention is to create success stories in different media, tailored to the different target audiences.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and scope

The key for a successful dissemination and communication strategy has been the application of a common framework, providing the consortium with a common process and a set of common criteria, with the purpose to identify, monitor and select the suited dissemination channels.

Another important parameter for the success of the dissemination plan is the direct involvement of all partners of the consortium in the process, especially those responsible for pilot implementation. All project partners have developed a sense of co-ownership of the project as they have been involved at all stages of the strategy's development. Each consortium member has responsibility for a particular aspect of the strategy's implementation, but also a shared vision and common understanding of what has to be disseminated together with a way of describing this to the audiences outside of the project that may benefit from the project work.

All dissemination activities have been in line with the protection of IPR as well as the confidentiality obligations, which were established in the Consortium Agreement (CA). All partners have actively engaged in the dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities conducted so far and are committed to continue along the lifespan of the project and beyond.

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of dissemination and communication activities carried out by the DIANA consortium during the first two years of the project. It will be updated at the end of the project in [D6.7 Report on the results of Dissemination activities \(2\)](#).

All activities have followed the DIANA Dissemination and Communication Strategy laid out in D6.1 and D6.2, which is briefly recapitulated below.

1.2. Key Elements of the DIANA Dissemination Strategy

The core objective of DIANA Dissemination and Communication Strategy (D6.1 and D6.2) is to provide a structure and roadmap for disseminating the concept, methodologies, pilots and outcomes of the project to particular audiences and to the wider public. In brief, the main objectives underpinning the DIANA strategy are to:

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- Raise awareness and provide high visibility of the project and later on of the product, among the target groups;
- Establish a strong brand identity from the beginning;
- Encourage involvement of other stakeholders;
- Raise awareness of policy makers and public bodies;
- Facilitate synergies with similar or complementary initiatives and;
- Promote, implement and spread the use of the service.

The expected results of the dissemination and communication strategy are: raising awareness; identification of target groups and how they can exploit project results; and promotion of active participation in the project.

The following sections provide a brief recapitulation of the definitions in D6.1 and D6.2 (Dissemination and Communication Strategy (1) and (2)).

1.2.1 Main assets disseminated

- DIANA data products and services aimed at enabling water management authorities to systematically and efficiently detect and estimate the level of non-authorized water abstractions for irrigation, pro-actively plan for and manage their water resources in drought conditions as well as better implement the WFD;
- DIANA service platform and its components including the web and mobile applications, the GIS dashboard and the REST API to be employed by all DIANA applications and modules for information retrieval and storage;
- Novel knowledge to be generated through the implementation of the project with respect to the application of EO derived data and technologies for identifying and estimating the amounts of irrigation water abstracted without authorisation in different operational, administrative, cultural and legal contexts across the EU;
- Data to be collected and produced in the frame of DIANA activities (e.g. EO-based, satellite, meteorological and ancillary data as well as data derived from the identification of the user requirements, the co-creation workshops, the evaluation and validation activities, etc.).

1.2.2 Target groups and audiences

Identifying the target groups has enabled the consortium to decide where and how to market DIANA in an effective and less costly way. Furthermore, segmenting the market has helped in identifying the similarities between the different target groups, as well as their differences, in order to better understand them and make the service and/or product more appealing and interesting to them.

In the table below we present the different target groups of DIANA and we also include a wider audience segment to which the action itself and its results will be communicated:

Table 1. Different target groups of DIANA.

Target group	Activity of target group	Example
Water managers	Responsible for monitoring and inspecting abstractions of water for irrigation	Public authorities or associations of irrigators depending on national/regional particularities
Authorities	Responsible for developing and implementing water/drought management plans and/or the WDF as well as issue irrigation water rights	River basin authorities, national, regional or local authorities
Farmers, agricultural cooperatives and consultancies	Active in the agricultural sector	Agribusiness professionals, advisors, innovation intermediaries
Research and Academia	Also with activities relevant to the agricultural sector	Academic institutions, non-university public research organisations, research and technology organisations
Non-governmental organisations and civic society groups	Interested in sustainable water management in the EU and aimed at addressing relevant social challenges and	Associations and NGOs

	needs	
Other Stakeholders	That may be interested in project outcomes	Policy and decision makers at EU level, etc
Wider public	People that have an interest on the issue	People that have an interest on the issue

2. Dissemination channels and results

This section provides a brief recapitulation of the dissemination materials and channels, as well as a summary of results. All details can be found in D6.2 (Dissemination and Communication Plan (2)), D6.3 (Promotional material), D6.4 (Social media accounts), and D6.5 (DIANA Web Portal). The emphasis is here on the results achieved.

2.1. Visual identity

An integrated and coherent visual identity underpins all communication products and tools and forms the basis for a commercial brand. The visual identity consists of the logo, colour pallet, and additional visual elements (e.g. the blue header bar used in templates) which work together to form a coherent and easily-recognisable whole.

By creating a comprehensive and clean logo, and investing in high-quality design, the WP6 team aimed to maximize and prolong the attention and interest of target audiences and convey the impression of a professional and operational undertaking, as opposed to a research project or a concept under development. In order to become widely recognizable as a brand with as much recognition and awareness as possible throughout the three years of the project.

As required by Horizon 2020 rules on dissemination (European Commission, 2012), across all the outputs of the DIANA project, and accompanying the logo, text concerning the source of the project's funding and disclosing the Grant Agreement number is provided, along with the European flag: *"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 730109"*.

The logo (see Figure 1) was created very early in the project, together with the associated colour palette. Based on these elements, the strong and coherent visual identity was also expressed in a series of templates, applied to the various project related documents: Deliverable documents;

Non-Deliverable Documents (such as memos, notes or letters); Deliverable document internal reviews; Event reports; Press releases; Presentations; Project Info Fact-Sheet; Project Poster; Project Brochure; Project Leaflet.

Figure 1: DIANA logo

This strong DIANA project visual identity is expected to also enhance and assist all exploitation and commercialisation actions (performed or planned) within WP5, towards the successful commercial exploitation of the project outputs (products and services) and the creation of a DIANA branding during and beyond the lifespan of the project, in accordance with the DIANA exploitation and commercialisation plan and related activities.

2.2. Website

The DIANA website (<http://diana-h2020.eu/>) was released in M04 (as described in detail in the deliverable D6.5 DIANA Web Portal) and represents a central point of dissemination for all target audiences. At this stage, the website contains information about the project (structure, objectives, concept, team, etc.) and can be used as a communication tool that assists partners in reaching stakeholders, as well as the wider audience. The project website has been further populated during the 2nd year of the project, focusing on improving and expanding the general information already provided with additional content (news, activities, events, etc.). The aim is to deliver content that attracts and raises the number of unique and returning visitors.

The website statistics, according to Google analytics, show a number of over 3000 visitors at the end of year 1 and over 8000 visitors at the end of year 2.

2.3. E-mail list and Newsletter

DIANA mailing list is continuously populated with new contacts and members, both from the website subscription button (self-registered subscriptions) but also from the consortium continuous engagement and networking activities. DIANA project updates and an electronic copy of the DIANA newsletter are being circulated to the mailing list in order to maintain

members' interest, increase engagement with the DIANA expanding community and leverage word-of-mouth communication about DIANA services.

During the 2nd year of the project a number of upscaling-actions have been executed, including the launch of the 1st DIANA newsletter, intensive networking activities, and expanding the DIANA email list with more members.

2.4. DIANA on Social Media

DIANA project has established a coherent social media presence, as described in detail in the deliverable D6.4 Social Media Accounts (M05). Active project accounts have been established in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube, engaging and interacting with followers.

Using social networks allows the DIANA project not only to reach and communicate with a large group of people nearly instantly, but also to disseminate value generated to the wide public.

Based on the consortium experience gained during the 1st year of the project, and in parallel to the continuous evaluation of the impact and reach generated through the different social media, the consortium decided to further customise them and assign specific project material to be circulated through each social media account.

Thus the Facebook account will be used for “wide public” dissemination actions, Twitter for wide public dissemination and synergies with “water related” influencers (Twitter represents the most dynamic way of communicating and cross-posting relevant news that are either DIANA originals or relevant third party/other organisation posts, building in this way greater awareness), LinkedIn for “Experts and Scientific community” dissemination purposes and YouTube for disseminating video material to all audiences (a variation of video material will be provided to address the various audience target groups).

Table 2. Social media channels of DIANA project.

Social Media Channel	Main type of Material
Facebook	Engagement material, infographics, meeting pictures, practical abstracts etc.
Twitter	Relevant conferences and events material
LinkedIn	Public deliverables, scientific publications, White papers
YouTube	Videos

The DIANA Twitter account can be found [here](#) and followed using '@H2020_DIANA'.

The DIANA Facebook account can be found [here](#).

The DIANA LinkedIn Group Page can be found [here](#).

The DIANA YouTube channel can be found [here](#).

2.5. Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

Table 3 shows the development of a number of Key Performance Indicators (KPI), as defined in D6.1. The expected target values have remained as initially defined.

Table 3. DIANA dissemination key performance indicators (KPI).

Performance Indicator	Target Value	1 st year	2 nd year	Means of verification
Visitors to the project website	6.000	3.004	8000	Google analytics
"Likes" on DIANA Facebook page	500	115	427*	Facebook account data
Followers of DIANA on Twitter	300	15	51	Twitter account data
Members on LinkedIn group	200	10	31	LinkedIn account data
Number of viewers of audiovisual material on YouTube	1000	n/a ⁹	149**	Number of views on YouTube
Publications on mass media	45	3	6	Dissemination reporting
Scientific publications	5	2	1	Dissemination reporting
Events to be attended by Project partners	10	9	12	Dissemination reporting
Newsletters produced	12	n/a	1	Copies available from reporting or via website
Number of subscribers to the newsletter	300	n/a	44	List of recipients

Number of contacts established in the Noi	200	17 mail lists	50	List of stakeholders
Number of distributed printed material	2000	200	>1500	Dissemination reporting

**427 following ** 23 subscribers*

3. Dissemination activities and results

All planned actions for the first and second year of the project have been carried out successfully and according to the plan. All consortium partners took part in the respective dissemination activities and contributed to achieving maximum attention and awareness beyond the project consortium.

All project partners are in a strong position to develop an effective “personal” dissemination strategy, building on key existing channels. These channels and links will provide direct access to the target groups and will act as core channels that will support the project’s sustainability and its effective exit strategy.

In the following sections, we examine all relevant activities carried out during the first two years of the project.

3.1. Network of Interest

The establishment and management of DIANA Network of Interest (NoI) has been and will be an ongoing activity during the entire life of the project, as well as after the end of the project. The main aim of establishing and expanding the “DIANA Network of Interest” is to have it act as a main dissemination pole for the engagement of DIANA target groups.

The DIANA NoI enables project partners to communicate the project objectives and disseminate its results on local, regional, national and European level. So far, the DIANA NoI counts 50 members. All NoI participants are encouraged to be involved in discussions concerning technical and scientific issues of the project through the official DIANA website, and they will be invited to participate in the project policy workshops.

Even though the effort is and will be to expand the NoI members list as a whole, special attention is given to attract those members that have the intention and the potential to utilise

the DIANA solution and, above all, to its future customers' base (those stakeholders who have the potential to purchase the solution).

3.2. Dissemination to scientific peers

This is the “classical” dissemination activities, essentially consisting of scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and oral presentation at scientific conferences (sometimes including a proceedings article published in a conference volume and/or with ppt presentations available online). It addresses the “Research and Academia” target group.

The DIANA consortium has so far produced three scientific papers in peer-reviewed journals, see Table 4 below. As of M24, several more papers are in preparation.

The oral presentations at scientific conferences and trainings are listed in Annex A (a total of seven). The DIANA partners have either presented the project as a whole or specific actions and results (scientific knowledge and methodologies emerging).

Table 4. Scientific Publications (Open Access).

Publication	Participating Partner details
<p>Negula, I. D.; Badea, A.; Moise, C.; Poenaru, V. (2017). "Earth observation satellite data in support of water management for agriculture", <i>AgroLife Scientific Journal</i> 2017 Vol.6 No.2 pp.133-136 ref.12.</p> <p>http://www.agrolifejournal.usamv.ro/pdf/vol.VI_2/Art19.pdf</p>	ROSA
<p>Alfonso Calera, Isidro Campos, Anna Osann, Guido D’Urso and Massimo Menenti. “Remote Sensing for Crop Water Management: From ET Modelling to Services for the End Users”, <i>Sensors</i> 2017, 17(5), 1104</p> <p>https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/5/1104</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3390/s17051104</p>	AgriSat/UCLM, Ariespace
<p>Poenaru, V., Badea, A., Cimpeanu, S., Irimescu, A. (2018). “Multi-temporal Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 time series analysis for the mapping of irrigated crops in the Great Island of Braila”,</p>	ROSA

Journal of Integrative Agricultures, under review.	
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3.3. Participation and presentation at industry events

Further to scientific publications, a complementary way to achieve an effective dissemination is the participation of project partners in targeted non-project events. This covers a wide range of industry events, from technology-oriented to policy-oriented. The DIANA consortium partners have been active in 25 events in various modalities: oral or poster presentations, keynotes, panel members, exhibitors, and networking participants. Annex C provides a list of the corresponding activities, which at the end of year 2 already exceed the initial target values.

3.4. DIANA stakeholder engagement events

The purpose of stakeholder engagement events is to interact with and mobilise regional and national stakeholder communities. The pilots form the nucleus of these events. Consequently, these stakeholder engagement events have been organized in Spain, in Romania, and in Italy. Some of these events have also been part of the continued co-creation process (WP1). Some of the events listed in Annex C (see section 3.2 above) have also served to enhance stakeholder engagement. Annex B provides the list of corresponding events, which at the end of year 2 already exceed the initial target values.

3.5. Mass media communication

Obtaining news coverage, whether at national or local level, increases the profile of the project to a great extent and enables the consortium to reach a very wide audience. The aim is to continue and utilise mass media communication activities to inform the general public about the DIANA project.

Table 5 provides a list of the dissemination of the project through TV and radio channels, web media, and newspapers and magazines - either printed or electronic.

Table 5. Mass media communications

Article or Press release	Responsible Partner	Audience Size
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Newspaper "La Repubblica/Napoli" 30 June, 2018 Article: La buona gestione dell'acqua.	Consorzio Sannio Alifano	with a circulation of about 377,000 copies.
Noticias: "Reunión en Albacete de los socios españoles del proyecto europeo Diana del H2020"	Feragua	with a circulation of about 7000.
"Feragua cierra su participación en un nuevo proyecto europeo Diana que se iniciara en enero de 2017"	Feragua	with a circulation of about 7000.
"Avances en la preparación del proyecto europeo Diana que comenzara en enero del año que viene"	Feragua	with a circulation of about 7000.
"Tesalónica acoge la reunión del lanzamiento del proyecto europeo Diana en que participa Feragua"	Feragua	with a circulation of about 7000.
MediaTV regional TV station broadcast "L'Appunto – Il Consorzio di Bonifica di Sannio Alifano nel progetto Diana"	Sannio Alifano	entire Campania region

3.6. Advisory Board

The Advisory Board is an integral part of DIANA project and its establishment assists the DIANA project to have access to valuable knowledge and expertise at all stages of the project implementation. Within that framework the Advisory Board also supports the project dissemination. Several Advisory Board members were present at important stakeholder engagement events.

4. Conclusions and next steps

All planned dissemination and communication actions for the first and second year of the project have been carried out successfully and according to plan, some of them exceeding the initial target values. All consortium partners have taken part in the respective dissemination activities and contributed to achieving maximum attention and awareness beyond the project consortium.

All dissemination activities have been in line with the protection of IPR as well as the confidentiality obligations, which were established in the Consortium Agreement (CA). All partners have actively engaged in the dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities conducted so far and are committed to continue along the lifespan of the project and beyond.

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The main assets disseminated have been: the DIANA data products and services; the DIANA service platform and its components including the web and mobile applications; novel knowledge generated through the implementation of the project; and the data collected during the pilot implementation.

The target groups and audience for dissemination have been water managers, authorities, farmers, agricultural cooperatives and consultancies, research and academia, NGOs and civil society groups, other stakeholders, and the general public.

The dissemination and communication material and activities that have been produced or undertaken during the first two years of the project include:

- the visual identity of the project, established at the beginning of the project, aiming to set the baseline for a brand identity for the commercial service;
- a public website launched in M05 and regularly updated, to serve as a single source of information concerning the project results and activities, and to disseminate news;
- the DIANA page on Facebook, the LinkedIn group and the DIANA Twitter account, which provide platforms for communicating news and material related to DIANA to specific audiences (e.g. younger, technologically-aware farmers on Facebook), and for sharing the latest information on the DIANA services;
- the first pilot area videos on DIANA YouTube channel;
- the first of the project's newsletters, providing information, results and events related to the project;
- specific dissemination materials used and distributed at external conferences (i.e. audience-focused presentations);
- representation in conferences and media as well as the publication of scientific papers, enhancing DIANA's visibility and enabling the development of a solid network amongst agricultural and Earth Observation (EO) academic and industrial stakeholders at both European and regional level.

All dissemination and communication activities are planned to be enhanced and amplified in the last project year. With convincing outcomes of pilot deployment and co-evaluation in hand, the intention is to create success stories in different media, tailored to the different target audiences.

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This project is co-funded by the European Union

Annexes

Annex A. Scientific conference oral presentations

Table 6. Scientific conference Oral Presentations

Scientific conference oral presentation	Audience Size
<p>8-13 April 2018</p> <p>Poenaru, V., Moise, C., Dana Negula, I.D., Badea, A., Vladucu, A., Mainerici, M., Stanisteanu, L. (2018). "Detection of irrigated crops from Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 data to estimate seasonal water use. A case study: Banat pilot area", EGU 2018, Vienna, Austria.</p> <p>https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU2018/EGU2018-19282.pdf</p>	1000
<p>7-9 June 2018</p> <p>Poenaru, V., Badea, A., Dana Negula, I.D., Moise, C., Cimpeanu, S. (2018). "Analysis of the Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 data for mapping irrigated crops in the Big Island of Braila", Agriculture for Life, Life for Agriculture Conference, Bucharest, Romania.</p>	50
<p>16 Nov 18. VII Agrometeorology Conference organized by the Ministry of Agriculture, Fish and Food. "Advances and challenges in the identification of irrigated areas and the use of water in irrigation through time series of images" A. Calera.</p> <p>https://twitter.com/natacarbonell/status/1063395035121623041</p>	100
<p>23 Nov.2018. Oral presentation at Technical meeting of the Agency for Development in Agriculture, Sardinia Region OZIERI (Sassari, Italy);</p> <p>Guido D'Urso "Applicazioni del telerilevamento da satellite per la gestione dell'irrigazione nelle colture foraggere, il progetto EU DIANA"</p> <p>– Ariespace.</p>	>30
<p>27 Nov 2018. Carlo De Michele, "Calcolo del fabbisogno irriguo delle coltivazioni con l'ausilio del satellite" Grottaminarda AV.</p>	24

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<p>28 Nov 18. Oral presentation at Technical conference on water management innovation through agro-climatic networks, remote sensing and Geographical Information Systems. <i>“Advances and challenges in the detection of irrigated surfaces and water management through time series of images: PROJECT H2020 DIANA”</i> A. Calera.</p> <p>https://www.agronomosalbacete.com/jornada-tecnica-sobre-innovacion-en-gestion-de-regadios-mediante-redes-agroclimaticas-imagenes-de-satelite-y-sistemas-de-informacion-geografica_center/</p>	50
<p>07 Dec. 2018 – (Salerno, Italy)</p> <p>Oral presentation at ‘Refresher course – Innovative experiences for the hydraulic management of the territory –’ C.U.G.R.I. – University Campus of Fisciano (Salerno, Italy);</p> <p>Utilizzo dei satelliti nell’agricoltura irrigua – Massimo Natalizio</p>	44

Annex B. Stakeholder engagement events and presentations

Table 7. Stakeholder engagement events and presentations

Event	Audience Size
20 Feb 2018 FERAGUA. Infor-day DIANA. Information on the state of the project and how it is developing to the Government Board of FERAGUA	25
22 May 2018 Ing. Massimo Natalizio (2018) – “Presentation of Sannio Alifano activities” – IRRI-DAY dedicated to irrigation in the Consortium Sannio Alifano Water policies, engine of life and investment for the rural economy – Ailano (CE) Presentazione 22-05-2018r.pdf	300
22 May 2018 Ing. Massimo Natalizio (2018) – “Illegal Irrigation Monitoring” – IRRI-DAY dedicated to irrigation in the Consortium Sannio Alifano Water policies, engine of life and investment for the rural economy – Ailano (CE).	300
22 May 2018 Guido D’Urso “Irrigazione innovativa nel Sannio Alifano: Progetti IRRISAT e DIANA” – IRRI-DAY dedicato all’irrigazione nel Sannio Alifano.	300
18 Jun 2018 FERAGUA. Infor-day DIANA. Information on the state of the project and how it is developing to the Government Board of FERAGUA.	25
3 Jul 2018 Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Environment, DIANA meeting with delegates from river-basin authorities.	11
02 Oct 2018 FERAGUA. Infor-day DIANA. Information on the state of the project and how it is developing to the Government Board of FERAGUA	25
30 Oct 2018 Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Environment, DIANA meeting	11

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with delegates from river-basin authorities.	
04 Dec 2018 FERAGUA. Infor-day DIANA. Information on the state of the project and how it is developing to the Government Board of FERAGUA.	25
10 Dec 2018 Madrid Spanish National Forum of Copernicus Users. Anna Osann “El Proyecto DIANA”	60

Annex C. Participation in events

Table 8. Participation of consortium in events

Title of Event	Aim of the event	Participating Partner details	Audience characteristics	Audience Size
OSTIA/Latina Italy. 08-09/02/2018	Presentation at AGROPONTINO E AGROROMANO Consortia (WUAs). In this technical meeting, technologies and expected impact of DIANA project have been presented to technicians and general manager of following irrigation and reclamation consortia: 1) Consorzio di Bonifica Tevere e Agro Romano, 2) Consorzio di Bonifica della Maremma Etrusca, 3) Consorzio di bonifica Pratica di Mare	Ariespace. DE MICHELE CARLO	Consorzio technicians and general managers	8
FIMA Zaragoza (ES) 20-24/02/2018,	40 International Fair of Agricultural machinery. https://www.feriazaragoza.es/fima-agricola-2018	AgriSat. Stand. AgriSat team	Farmers, companies linked with the agricultural sector. Innovation agri-machinery	240.000
LATINA. Italy. 09/03/2018	Presentation at AGROPONTINO Consortium (WUA)	Ariespace. DE MICHELE CARLO	WUAs	30
Feragua General Meeting. Sevilla. SP. 03/04/2018	The general meeting of Feragua takes place in Seville once per year. Most important items of the association are discussed and projects where Feragua is actively participating are presented.	Presented by: Elena Navarro Soriano and Pedro	Managers from the WUAs and presidents are the audience.	50

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		Parias. Entity: FERAGU A		
CAGLIARI. Italy. 15/05/2018	Presentation at SARDEGNA Consortia (WUAs). In this technical meeting, technologies and expected impact of DIANA project have been presented to technicians and general manager of following irrigation and reclamation consortia: 1) Consorzio di Bonifica NORD SARDEGNA, 2) Consorzio di Bonifica della SARDEGNA CENTRALE, 3) Consorzio della SARDEGNA MERIDIONALE, 4) Consorzio di Bonifica dell'Ogliastra	Ariespace. DE MICHEL E CARLO	WUAs	11
IRRI-DAY dedicated to irrigation in the Consortium Sannio Alifano. Ailano (CE). 22/05/2018.	<p>http://www.sannioalifano.it/news/423-settimana-nazionale-della-bonifica-e-dell-irrigazione-2.html</p> <p>http://www.sannioalifano.it/images/file/2017/invito_diana1.pdf</p> <p>The aim of the event was the commitment of the Sannio Alifano Reclamation Consortium in practice of new technologies in agriculture, like the use of satellite images IRRISAT - DIANA, for a lawful, more efficient and environmentally sustainable management of water resources.</p>	Ing. M. Natalizio. Sannio Alifano Prof. Guido D'URSO. Ariespace	Farmers, Scientific community, Local Water managing authorities, members of Campania Region, Policy stakeholders, Mayors of the municipalities of the Sannio Alifano area, etc.	300

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<p>FOOD 2030 Food Village exhibition, in Plovdiv (Bulgaria). 14-15/06/2018</p>	<p>Food 2030 priorities: Nutrition for healthy and sustainable diets, Climate and environmental sustainability, Circularity and resource efficiency, Innovation and empowering communities.</p> <p>Specific objectives of the Conference are to unfold the systemic nature of food and nutritional systems and build R&I ecosystems to provide solutions to food systems transformation, to strengthen the potential for R&I cooperation and coordination/alignment at different levels (within MSs, among the MSs and with the EU), including future investments in R&I in Europe and leveraging private investments and increasing synergies with public funding.</p>	<p>Anna Osann, María Calera (AgriSat) Stelios Kotsopoulos, Gregory Mygdakos (AgroApps)</p>	<p>Flagship Conference 2nd FOOD 2030 High Level Event</p>	<p>250</p>
<p>GFIA, Utrecht (NL) 20-21/06/2018</p>	<p>Global forum for innovations in agriculture.</p>	<p>AgriSat. Anna Osann. Andrés Cuesta Sponsor & Stand</p>	<p>Scientific community, authorities, policy makers.</p>	<p>300</p>
<p>II CONGRESS ON FERTILIZATION. 25-26 Aug 18</p>	<p>Fertilizers and biotechnology, walking towards the future.</p>	<p>Vicente Bodas. Andrés Cuesta. AgriSat. Participation with Stand and sponsor</p>	<p>Farmers.</p>	<p>1500</p>
<p>INSPIRE 2018 Antwerp 17-19/09/18</p>	<p>https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/conference2018</p> <p>Following the digital transition that is firmly taking shape, we now stand on the brink of a green transition. The Paris Agreement on Climate Change fuels the energy transition in the world. Circular economy principles, in which we consider waste to be resources, are increasingly incorporated in local</p>	<p>Dimitra Perperidou, AgroApps</p>	<p>SMEs, Universities, EU stakeholders, Experts</p>	<p>40</p>

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	<p>policy. Meanwhile administrations, research institutes and curious and involved citizens monitor the natural environment they live in and care for. At the interface of these different actors lies a fundamental asset of the INSPIRE Directive: the obstacle free sharing of geospatial data and information across all levels of government and borders!</p>			
<p>ETAGRO 2018. Thessaloniki, Greece. 01-02/11/2018</p>	<p>http://etagro.gr/2018/ The aim of the 15th Panhellenic Conference of Agricultural Economy was to re-evaluate the development of rural areas in the contemporary digital age.</p>	<p>Dimitra Perperidou, AgroApps</p>	<p>SMEs, Universities, Experts.</p>	<p>40</p>
<p>24th MARS Conference Dubrovnik, Croatia. 21-22/11/2018</p>	<p>https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/event/conference/24th-mars-conference The conference provided a platform to present and discuss Member States' experiences and general observations regarding the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS), including developments in shared management</p>	<p>Dimitra Perperidou AgroApps</p>	<p>SMEs, Universities, EU stakeholder s, Experts</p>	<p>300</p>
<p>23/11/2018. Agency for Development in Agriculture , Sardinia</p>	<p>Laore Sardegna Agency has organized a meeting on "satellite remote sensing for the management of fodder crops in irrigated areas". The aim of the meeting is the technological innovations for the sustainable use of water resources, the role and organization of irrigation areas, with particular reference http://www.agronomiforestali.av.it/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=342:giornata-formativa-al-consorzio-di-bonifica-dellufita&catid=1:ultime&Itemid=5to the Northern Sardinia Reclamation District</p>	<p>Guido D'Urso. Ariespace</p>	<p>Livestock companies, users and operators of irrigation areas</p>	<p>30</p>
<p>Training day DIANA. GROTTAMI NARDA (Avellino),</p>	<p>http://www.sardegnaagricoltura.it/index.php?xsl=443&s=379132&v=2&c=3572&vd=1 "Calculation of irrigated crop requirements with</p>	<p>Consorzio di Bonifica dell'Ufita. Carlo de</p>	<p>Agronomist and practitioners in</p>	<p>24</p>

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ITALY 27/11/2018	the satellite data" followed by a guided tour of the hydraulic works carried out by the Reclamation Consortium.	Michele. Ariespace	agriculture.	
EU Agricultural Outlook Conference 2018. Brussels 6-7/12/2018	Oral presentation at the EU Agricultural Outlook conference that has now become the key annual gathering of European stakeholders willing to engage and discuss the future of agriculture in Europe and the challenges which lie ahead.	Anna Osann-AgriSat	Agriculture sector	600 plus livestream
National Forum of Copernicus users. 10 Dec 18 Madrid	National Forum of Copernicus users, at AEMET (Spanish Meteorological Agency), presentation of DIANA	Anna Osann. AgriSat	Copernicus Users	60
Agro Expo	Cooperation in the Abona Global Stand at Agro Expo. Agroexpo is the International Fair dedicated to agriculture that is held annually in Badajoz and which stands out above all for its extensive program of technical conferences, in which talks and presentations of great interest are given. It is one of the agricultural events of reference for the sector.	AgriSat. Carmen Plaza, Vicente Bodas, Andrés Cuesta.	Business, Farmers, Machinery	70.000
Copernicus for agriculture	Organized by DG-GROW. Presentation of DIANA by policy officer. The aim of the workshop is to address the possible role of the private (downstream) sector for possible solutions, integrating Copernicus data and Copernicus services' information, in support of the agricultural end-users at the different levels: international, European and Member States' level.	AgriSat. Anna Osann	The Agriculture sector	400
SNIH18 – III Simposio Nacional de Ingeniería Hortícola	Drones and Remote Sensing for Agricultural use.	AgriSat. Carmen Plaza	Farmers, Researchers.	200

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XIV Congreso Nacional de Comunidades de Regantes de España	This Congress was a meeting for analysis on the main concerns that affect the national government sector related to water policy. https://congresoregantesalicante.org/	AgriSat. María Calera, María Llanos López.	Water User Associations, farmers	1000 Aprox.
14th ICPA	International Conference on Precision Agriculture (ICPA) presented by the International Society of Precision Agriculture (ISPA) was held in Montreal, Quebec, Canada during the last week of June.	AgriSat. María Calera.	AgriGood community.	300
InfoAg Conference	Since 1995, the InfoAg Conference has been the premier event for discussion and advancement of precision agriculture. This event draws interest from domestic and international agriculture professionals and features a wide range of educational and networking opportunities for professionals interested in learning more about precision agriculture techniques.	AgriSat. Anna Osann, María Calera.	domestic and international agriculture professionals	2500
Remote sensing for crop classification and mapping.	C.U.A.S. (Community of Underground Water Users) Rus Valdelobos. Cuenca (Spain)	María Calera. Carmen Plaza AgriSat.	Community of Groundwater Users	13
EU Space Week Marseille 4 Dec 2018	The EU Space week will gather leaders from the public sector and industry to discuss how European Satellite Navigation and Earth Observation serve as a powerful tool in tackling today's economic, social, and environmental challenges and creating opportunities for game-changing growth.	Anna Osann. AgriSat. Business roundtable	Leaders from the public sector and industry	1000

